

SHEAR CHARACTERISATION OF UNIDIRECTIONAL AND FABRIC REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES FOR PRESSFORMING APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes research carried out to examine the forming mechanisms occurring during the pressforming of thermoplastic composite laminates. These include interply slip of individual plies, and the 'trellis' shearing mechanism unique to fabrics. Tow stretching can occur in fabrics to alleviate forming stresses and strains. Interply slip deformations were measured using 90°-bend parts. The shear velocity/shear stress relationship was characterised for CF/PEI 'Cetex' fabric using a shearing apparatus (including temperature and pressure effects). A power law model was developed which incorporates tow stretching. A kinematic model for fabric 'trellis' deformations was validated experimentally and used to estimate viscosity components.

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic composites offer many advantages over more traditional thermoset materials such as increased toughness, better fatigue capability and indefinite shelf life [1]. However, it is their potential rapid-processing capabilities that show most promise for future development. One such technique developed over the past number of years has been pressforming, adapted from the metal-forming industry. Using this method, laminates can be heated to processing temperature in 1-2 minutes e.g. by using infra-red heating, transferred between the forming dies, pressed into shape in seconds and removed. However, problems such as non-isothermal conditions during forming, ply buckling and fibre breakage have resulted in poor part quality and necessitated further research. One method of circumventing possible problems would be to use a numerical simulation of the pressforming process, in which the designer or manufacturer could simulate the forming stages and allow a prediction of final part quality, avoiding expensive mould re-design and re-work. A EU-funded Brite/EuRam project has been initiated to develop a suitable software package, involving partners from 4 different countries [2]. The work described in this paper forms part of a larger sub-task in the project, involving basic investigation of forming mechanisms and the development of material laws to be implemented in the software.

EXPERIMENTAL

FORMING OF 90°-BEND PARTS

To investigate the interply slip mechanism as it occurs during the forming of both unidirectional and fabric laminates [3], a simple 90°-bend geometry was formed from flat laminates and the amount of slip at the part edges measured. Assuming inextensible fibres, conservation of thickness (no 'squeeze' flow) and no buckling, the theoretical amount of slip required at the edge (d) can be found from simple geometrical considerations to be given by:

$$d = \frac{N\theta t}{2} \quad (1)$$

where N = total number of plies, θ = mould bend angle and t = ply thickness.

Figure 1. 90°-bend forming apparatus

Fig. 1 shows the forming apparatus that was used. It consists of two integrally-heated male/female matched dies, contained in an environmental chamber (400°C capability). Pressing force was achieved using a hydraulically driven actuator, 60 kN capacity, with possible forming speeds of between 1 and 100 mm/s. The laminate edges were ground square before forming. After allowing the moulds to come to temperature, the pre-consolidated coupon was allowed to heat for 5 minutes. The male die was then lowered at 10 mm/s causing the part to deform into the bend. After cooling under pressure, the part was removed, sectioned and mounted for micrographic analysis.

Results using the carbon fibre/PEEK unidirectional material ('APC-2', $t = 0.125$ mm) show good agreement between measured and predicted values. Fig. 2(a) shows the edge deformation in a $(0,90,0,90)_S$ laminate where the plies are seen to behave as rigid plates, with interply slip occurring between plies. A thin resin layer was observed to exist between the plies in a cross-ply layup. This layer is approximately $6\ \mu\text{m}$ thick and is important for interply slip to occur. The resin in the layer is assumed to behave as a viscous fluid flowing between parallel plates i.e. Couette flow. In Fig. 2(b), slip can be seen in a quasi-isotropic $(0,+45,90,-45)_S$ layup. Comparing the measured slip amount d with that predicted by eqn. (1), the slip seen in the $0/90$ laminate is 0.88 mm (101% of the predicted value) whereas for the quasi layup, the deformation is 0.69 mm or 93.6% of the predicted amount. Slip was also observed in a unidirectional $(0)_8$ laminate, as shown in Fig. 2(c). However, rather than interply slip between plies being the dominant mechanism, intraply shearing seems to occur evenly across the whole thickness i.e. the entire laminate behaves as a single ply. No distinct resin layer is evident between the plies, therefore, no interply slip can occur. However, the deformation d (0.65 mm) represents 98.3% of the predicted value.

Figure 2. Interply slip in APC-2 laminates

For fabrics, inextensibility of the fibres (or fibre 'tows') may not be assumed - due to the nature of the fabric weave, the tows have the ability to 'stretch' slightly under tensile loading, allowing the ply to elongate and accommodate any required interply slip deformation to a certain degree. Beyond a critical amount of tensile stress, interply slip becomes the preferred deformation mechanism. This was evidenced in formed parts made from 5-H satin weave carbon fibre/PEI ('Cetex', $t = 0.33$ mm) laminates. Fig. 3(a) shows a part made with a 'short' flange length of 20 mm, and Fig. 3(b) a part with a 'long' flange length of 60 mm. The term 'flange length' relates to that length of the deforming ply along which tow stretching may occur (Fig. 3(c)). The longer the flange, the more stretching may occur. The amount of slip in the 'long'-flanged part ($d = 0.075$ mm) represents only 9.8% of the predicted value, whereas there is 0.315 mm or 41.8% of that predicted in the 'short' flange.

Figure 3. Interply slip in 5-H Cetex fabric laminates

STRETCH TESTING OF 'CETEX' FABRIC

To further investigate the tensile stresses and strains involved in stretching of fabrics during forming, single sheet tensile specimens (30 x 100 mm²) of the Cetex material were tested in an environmental chamber (T = 320°C) using an Instron tensile testing machine. Two material forms were investigated: (i) plain weave and (ii) 5-H satin weave. Fig. 4 shows the obtained stress/strain plot. The behaviour shows that there is an initial strain in the fabric before the stress begins to increase exponentially. The plain weave pattern allows for more tow stretching compared with the 5-H satin weave specimen. The stress/strain behaviour of the 5-H satin weave material can be modelled as follows:

$$\sigma = 0.03061 \exp^{2.1003(\epsilon)} \quad (2)$$

where σ = tensile stress, ϵ = strain (change in specimen length/original specimen length)

This model was used to predict tensile stresses in the fabric as it is strained and will be used in the next section to provide an understanding of the interply slip behaviour of fabric laminates as they are being formed.

Figure 4. Stretching of Cetex fabric specimens

INTERPLY SLIP CHARACTERISATION OF FABRIC LAMINATES

The 90°-bend parts that were formed showed that interply slip does occur as a forming mechanism for fabric laminates, but in a more complex fashion compared to that for unidirectional materials. Previous research has involved characterising the interply slip mechanism for unidirectional materials, and establishing the shear velocity/shear stress relationship as a function of the process parameters (temperature, pressure and fibre orientation) [4]. Using the same experimental testing

rig as in [4], a series of 'ply-pullout' experiments were carried out on 5-H Cetex laminates, to investigate the effects of varying the various process parameters. Fig. 5 shows a schematic of the shearing apparatus.

Figure 5. 'Ply-pullout' experimental test apparatus

Applying a constant normal pressure of 100 kPa to the heated sample, pullout was initiated by using the shearing apparatus to apply a traction force to the central ply in the test layup. The response in Fig. 6 shows that initial stretching of the ply is followed by a transition (point A) to shearing behaviour between the plies, followed by a velocity (shear rate) dependent stationary level of shear force/stress (point B). The behaviour of a typical (0,90,0)_S APC-2 specimen indicates that there is no initial fibre stretching. Instead the response is elasto-viscous in nature (stable at point C). For 5-H Cetex, the point at which behaviour changes from tow stretching to ply shearing can be inferred from the point of inflexion of the time/force plot. This lies at 55 N, or at 5.5 kPa shearing stress for the 100 mm x 50 mm sample. This value appears independent of temperature and pressure effects, but further tests would be needed to verify this. This figure may be related to eqn. (2) by comparing tensile forces in the shearing ply with shear stress in the interlayer. By knowing the tensile response to an applied strain in the ply (Figure 4), we can find the tensile stress if the flange length L_f along which stretching can occur is also known, and by equating tensile/shearing forces (assuming constant width), this results in:

$$\sigma = \frac{\tau L_f}{t_p} = \frac{(5.5 \text{ kPa}) L_f}{0.33 \text{ mm}} = 1.667e7 L_f \quad (3)$$

where L_f = flange length (mm), t_p = ply thickness (0.33 mm for 5-H Cetex).

Figure 6. Pullout test on unidirectional/fabric material

This allows determination of deformation behaviour before interply slip is initiated. If the flange length is insufficient and the 5.5 kPa shear stress in the interlayer is exceeded, then a velocity dependent viscous shear behaviour develops. Experiments to characterise this were carried out by performing pullout tests at various shearing velocities (0-0.5 mm/s) and measuring the stable shear stress response.

Figure 7. Interply slip of 5-H Cetex - temperature effects

The effect of temperature on shear stress/shear velocity is shown in Fig. 7. As expected, an increase in temperature has the effect of reducing shear stress for a particular shearing velocity, which is similar to results for unidirectional materials [4]. This is the result of a decrease in matrix viscosity, and hence resistance to flow at the interface between plies, at higher temperatures. An increase of 40°C, from 300° to 340°C causes a substantial reduction ($\approx 50\%$) in shear stress at typical velocities between 0.1 and 0.2 mm/s. Thus, high forming temperatures may be recommended for forming of fabric thermoplastic composites when possible. Problems such as fibre washing of surface fibres do not happen to the same extent as unidirectional materials due to the constraints imposed by the fabric weave. Surface oxidation may be a problem at excessively high temperatures.

Interply shearing tests were also performed with applied normal pressures in the range 20 to 400 kPa. The obtained shear velocity/shear stress relationship is shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 8. Interply slip of 5-H Cetex - normal pressure effects

Load cell limitations on the shearing apparatus reduced the attainable shearing velocity to approximately 0.25 mm/s at higher normal pressures. As with APC-2, a significant increase in shear stress is seen as the pressure is increased. The magnitude of the recorded stresses are much higher compared with the unidirectional material. Even allowing for matrix and viscosity differences, there is a much greater resistance to interply slip for the Cetex material, again probably due to the nature of the interaction between adjoining plies, with much more interference to sliding being caused by the uneven surface of the woven plies. A relatively constant resin layer cannot be assumed to exist between the fabric plies, unlike unidirectional materials [4].

To model the observed viscous-like behaviour, an adapted form of the Herschel-Buckley power law fluid model is used [5]. This predicts the shear stresses developed in the interlayer between plies as a function of shearing velocity, temperature and pressure:

$$\tau(V, T, P) = \tau_0 + k.(V)^n \quad (4)$$

where τ = shear stress (kPa), τ_0 = 'yield' stress = 5.5 kPa, V = shearing velocity (mm/s).

The values for the multiplier k and exponent n may be written as a function of the process parameters (temperature and pressure) by curve-fitting using a least squares regression technique to a plot of k/n vs. temperature/pressure. For temperature variation, the following was obtained (model shown in Fig. 7):

$$\tau(V, T) = \tau_0 + k.(V)^n \quad (5)$$

where $k = -752.71 + 5.8641(T) - 1.0435e-2(T)^2$, $n = -16.064 + 0.10194(T) - 1.5689e-4(T)^2$

Similarly, for normal pressure variation (as in Fig. 8):

$$\tau(V, P) = \tau_0 + k.(V)^n \quad (6)$$

where $k = 11.52 + 0.50812(P) - 7.0862e-4(P)^2$, $n = 0.50791 - 2.1394e-4(P)$

Due to the biaxial nature and symmetry of the fabric weave, it was assumed that the relative orientation of the fibres between two neighbouring plies had no effect on the slippage behaviour (as opposed to the unidirectional material APC-2) and thus no fibre angle effects are included.

The models for temperature and pressure may be combined by applying a standard set of parameters to each model ($T = 320^\circ\text{C}$ and $P = 100$ kPa) to obtain τ_s . Then by using a factoring technique, the following may be obtained:

$$\tau(V, T, P) = \frac{\tau(V, T)}{\tau_s} \cdot \frac{\tau(V, P)}{\tau_s} \cdot \tau_s \quad (7)$$

where $\tau(V, T)$ and $\tau(V, P)$ are given above by eqn. (5) and (6) and $\tau_s = 5.5 + 55.246(V)^{0.49021}$.

This model is valid for melt-phase forming of 5-H Cetex fabric for the following conditions:

$$300 < T < 340^\circ\text{C}$$

$$20 < P < 400 \text{ kPa}$$

$$0 < V < 0.5 \text{ mm/s}$$

INVESTIGATION OF THE 'TRELLIS' MECHANISM IN GF/PA-12 FABRIC

Another mechanism unique to fabrics when undergoing 3-D forming deformations is the so-called 'trellis' effect, as shown in Fig. 9. This relates to the change in relative fibre angle between tows in the warp and weft directions as the material is strained.

Figure 9. 'Trellis' mechanism in fabrics

A constitutive theory has been developed by Johnson [6], based on the concept of an Ideal Fibre Reinforced Fluid [7], extended to include two families of fibres. The development of the relevant constitutive equations are not dealt with here. Instead, a number of validation tests were performed to (i) examine the deformation of a $\pm 45^\circ$ oriented fabric sheets stretched in the vertical direction and

(ii) to measure and compare the stresses in the X-direction and allow approximations for the three material viscosities η_1, η_2 and η_3 . These independent viscosities describe the viscous shear flow in the material. The first two, η_1 and η_2 , are related to the shear in the longitudinal (along the fibres) and transverse (across the fibres) directions respectively. However, they do not each correspond to a single shearing mode, as is the case for unidirectional materials. The third, η_3 , only becomes active when the angle (ϕ) between the two sets of fibres changes. This describes the 'trellis' viscosity. The 'trellis' angle θ may be described by, from [6]:

$$\cos \theta = \cos \theta_0 \exp(\epsilon_{11}) \tag{8}$$

where θ ='trellis' angle, θ_0 =initial angle between tows ($=45^\circ$), ϵ_{11} =true axial strain

This relationship is purely kinematic in nature and was validated by performing stretch tests at a constant strain rate (λ) on a $\pm 45^\circ$ -oriented glass fibre/PA-12 fabric, and measuring the trellis angle at the centre of the sample. An Instron tensile testing machine with a 1kN load cell was used to apply force in the X-direction. The comparison between measured trellis angle and that predicted by eqn. (8) is shown in Fig. 10.

Figure 10. 'Trellis' angle as function of applied strain

There is reasonable agreement between measured and predicted values: differences may be caused by difficulty in determining the true axial strain due to restrictions placed on fibre rotation at the grips. The 'locking' angle was determined as the angle at which out-of-plane buckling of the sample was first observed, and indicates the minimum 'trellis' angle attainable due to bunching of the fibre tows. This value lies between 25° and 30° , in accordance with the angle observed by other researchers for this material [8]. This angle may be considered a failure criterion for forming.

Stress in the X or 1-1 direction may be related to trellis angle, strain rate and viscosities η_1, η_2 and η_3 by:

$$\sigma_{11} = \lambda [4\eta_1 - (3\eta_1 - 2\eta_2)\sin^2 2\theta - \frac{1}{4}\eta_3 \sin^2 4\theta] / \sin^4 \theta \tag{9}$$

By measuring the force required to stretch a $\pm 45^\circ$ sample at a strain rate λ , at various temperatures, and by knowing the trellis angle from eqn. (8), values for the three viscosities may be approximated by fitting eqn. (9) to the obtained stress/true strain curve, as shown in Fig. 11.

The viscosity parameters are shown in Table 1. The value of η_3 best approximated experimental data by being set equal to zero i.e. insignificant compared to the other two terms. These values are only approximations and inhomogenous straining of the sample may have introduced errors. More extensive testing of samples at varying strain rates and across a full range of temperatures is necessary for full flow characterisation of GF/PA-12 fabric. Note that these viscosities do not represent actual 'real' values, but may be considered as 'virtual' viscosity parameters that fit the experimental data. It is not possible to say whether η_2 should increase with temperature in actuality, as indicated by the available test results.

Temperature (°C)	η_1 (Pa.s)	η_2 (Pa.s)	η_3 (Pa.s)
265°	1.2e7	7.0e6	0
245°	3.0e7	3.5e6	0
225°	4.0e7	3.0e6	0

Table 1. Viscosity parameter values

Figure 11. Stress/strain plot for $\pm 45^\circ$ -GF/PA-12 specimen at various temperatures

CONCLUSIONS

Interply slip has been observed in both UD and fabric-reinforced 90° -bend parts. Tow stretching in fabrics reduces the required slip deformations to prevent buckling. A strain-dependent stretching modulus for 5-H satin weave Cetex has been determined by experiment. This, in conjunction with interply slip tests carried out under varying conditions of temperature and pressure, has allowed the development of a power law model which predicts shear stresses in the interlayer between plies as a function of applied strain in the plies and interply shearing velocity. The deformation characteristics of a GF/PA-12 fabric sheet have been examined to measure the 'trellis' angle during shearing. The three viscosity parameters η_1 , η_2 and η_3 have been estimated as a function of temperature.

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